

Effect Of Aerobic Exercises on Quality of Life in Perimenopausal Women

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ABSTRACT

Background: Perimenopause is a transitional phase characterised by fluctuating hormone levels that often lead to symptoms such as hot flashes, mood disturbances, sleep irregularities, and reduced physical functioning. These changes can significantly affect a woman's quality of life. Non-pharmacological approaches, especially aerobic exercise, may play a valuable role in alleviating these symptoms.

Material and Methodology: The sample of this experimental study was composed of 22 perimenopausal women between the ages of 40 and 49 years. Quality of life baseline estimation was done through the MENQOL questionnaire. The experimental group was subjected to an aerobic exercise programme of 45 minutes per day, five days per week, and a period of four weeks followed by a control group that went about with their normal undertakings. The same tool was used to assess the post-intervention outcomes. Paired and unpaired t-tests, Chi-square tests, Wilcoxon signed-rank tests, and Mann-Whitney U tests were all used as statistical analysis.

Results: The vasomotor, psychological and physical domains of the MENQOL had significant improvements in the experimental group ($p < 0.05$) whereas no meaningful improvement was observed in the control group. Non-significant progress was shown in the sexual domain. Statistically significant decrease in the total MENQOL scores was also seen in the exercise group which suggests improvement in the overall quality of life.

Conclusion: Frequent aerobic work significantly improves the stability of the vasomotor system, emotional state, and physical comfort of perimenopausal women. It is an effective, inexpensive and easily available intervention to enhance quality of life in menopausal transition.

Keywords: Perimenopause, Aerobic exercise, Quality of life, MENQOL, Hormonal transition.

INTRODUCTION:

Perimenopause is the biological transition preceding menopause and it normally starts in late 30s to mid40s. It is characterized by hormonal variation especially the decreased concentrations of estrogen and progesterone which lead to menstrual abnormalities and diverse physical and emotional manifestations.^[1] These can incorporate vasomotor disorders (hot flashes and night sweats), mood fluctuations, anxiety, irritability, joint pains, sleep problems, and decreased sexual functions. These symptoms interfere with the normal functioning of many women and have a detrimental effect on the life quality.^[2]

The changes in the activity of hormones during perimenopause affect a number of body regulatory systems. Rapid changes in estrogen levels (high or low) influence thermoregulation, mood (through neurotransmitters such as serotonin), musculoskeletal, sleep and cognitive functioning. Consequently, the period of perimenopause is usually accompanied by physical, emotional, and lifestyle restrictions.^[3]

One of these has been identified as aerobic exercise as one of the most effective non-pharmacological intervention strategies to improve hormonal balance, reduce stress, and increase physical and emotional resilience. Working out enhances a healthy metabolism of estrogens, raises the levels of endorphins and dopamine, increases heart fitness, and maintains sleep and mood. Its efficacy in helping to relieve menopausal symptoms is a topic that has been studied by different authors but there is a need to conduct more studies on perimenopausal women.^[4]

Since exercise has some potential in enhancing the overall well-being, this research aims to determine the effect of structured aerobic exercise programme on the quality of life in perimenopausal women, as the validated outcome measure, MENQOL questionnaire.^[5]

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY:

The study design implemented was experimental, in order to compare the impacts of aerobic exercise and normal lifestyle activities in perimenopausal women, in terms of quality of life. The total sample size was 22 who were recruited using convenience sampling and randomly divided into: Experimental (n=11) Group - received aerobic exercise intervention and Control (n=11) Group - who continued with their daily routine activities. The OpenEpi was used to calculate the sample size at 99% confidence interval and 90% power. The research was carried out in the Pune city within six months. MENQOL (Menopause-Specific Quality of Life Questionnaire) was used as the outcome measure as it evaluates four domains: vasomotor,

psychological, physical, and sexual. Women aged 40-49 years, working women or homemakers with perimenopause symptoms (3-6 months) were involved in the study. Women with acute injuries/recent fracture, cardiovascular/respiratory conditions, neurological conditions, known gynecological conditions, regular yoga/exercise participants and diabetes, hypertension, and obesity (Class I/II) were excluded.

PROCEDURE:

The Institutional Ethics Committee of St. Andrews college of Physiotherapy gave ethical approval. Potential members were told about the researched work and signed a written agreement. After the collection of demographic data, the participants were randomly divided into two groups. All participants were baseline MENQOL scored. The experimental group received Intervention Protocol and was allowed 4 weeks of duration of 5 days/week about 45 minutes/session; 10 min warm-up and 25 to 30 minutes aerobic exercises plus 10 minutes cool-down. The control group would go on with their daily routine activities and would not be under any structured exercise training. The two groups were, again, measured after 4 weeks, with the use of the MENQOL questionnaire. Appropriate tests were used to analyze data.

RESULTS:

Twenty-two participants were recruited into the research with ten women in the experimental and ten in the control group. The two groups had an equal age distribution without any significant differences ($p>0.05$). The occupation difference was very high among groups but the other baseline factors were similar. In vasomotor domain, experimental group displays a significant improvement ($p=0.008$) at the end of the intervention period compared to the control group ($p>0.05$). This suggests the effectiveness of aerobic exercise in night sweats and hot flushes. Equally, there is high improvement in the domain of psychology of symptoms ($p=0.000$) in experimental group and no significant difference in Control group. Findings of mood swings, anxiety, irritability, and sleep issues were decreased significantly in women who worked out. In physical domain, experimental group: exhibits a substantial improvement ($p=0.001$) and the control group displays insignificant non-improvement. As the fatigue, stiffness in the joints, low energy, and physical discomfort lessened with the conduction of aerobic activities. Alternatively, in sexual domain neither of the groups exhibited significant improvements ($p>0.05$) since many of the participants were reluctant to express sexual concerns, and this could have influenced the responses. The total MENQOL score suggests that

there was a highly significant change ($p=0.000$) in the experimental group and slight but statistically significant change ($p=0.033$) in the control group, which is probably attributed to natural time-related changes as opposed to intervention. On the whole, exercised women achieved much more in several areas of life.

Graph 1: Within-Group (Pre vs. Post Intervention) Analysis

Graph 2: Post intervention Mean Value

DISCUSSION:

The study has explored the impact of aerobic exercise to quality of life among perimenopausal women and concluded that there was significant improvement in post-intervention vasomotor, psychological, and physical domains of quality of life.

Vasomotor Domain

The levels of hot flashes and night sweats decreased significantly in four weeks of aerobic exercise. The hypothalamus thermoregulatory center becomes more stable during regular exercise when blood circulation becomes better and the endorphins control the means of heat-loss. Similar results have been reported by Khan SJ et al. (2023) ^[6] and Elavsky (2009) ^[7], that have demonstrated that exercise has the ability to suppress vasomotor distress and enhance autonomic stability.

Psychological Domain

Regular physical activity enhances the activity of dopamine and serotonin that are necessitating neuro transmitters of mood. Women undergoing aerobic exercise were found to have a better emotional balance, lower anxiety levels and better sleep routine. These results of present study are consistent with those of Chattha et al. (2008) ^[8] and Sternfeld et al. (2014) ^[9], that have given exercise as a natural mood stabiliser.

Physical Domain

Aerobic training enhances oxygen, muscle efficiency, joint movement and endurance. The experimental group felt less exhausted and more physically able, which is in line with those of Zhao Yi et al. (2022) ^[10], that exercise improves physical performance and lessens physical fatigue brought on by hormonal fluctuations in middle-aged women.

Sexual Domain

The sexual domain was not significantly changed and this could be explained by the cultural reluctance to talk about intimacy or the necessity of more intensive and more prolonged interventions.

Overall Outcome

The four weeks programme showed that the easy and accessible aerobic exercises can add practical changes to the various areas of daily functioning in perimenopause. Aerobic exercise is a good choice of non-pharmacological methods since it is cheap, has no side effects, and is easy to undertake by any women.

CONCLUSION:

The study concludes that systematic aerobic training makes a great contribution to the quality of life of perimenopausal women by mitigating vasomotor symptoms, enhancing psychological balance, and improving physical well-being. Though there was minimal change in sexual symptoms, the general outcome depicts that aerobic exercise is safe, effective, and low-cost intervention.

By convincing women to include a structured aerobic activity into their daily schedule, one is likely to help them overcome the difficulties of hormonal transition more easily and without any fear.

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